

TEACHER'S MONITORING OF LEARNERS ON MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING AND ITS EFFECT ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE THREE PUPILS IN SANTA CRUZ NORTH DISTRICT, DIVISION OF MARINDUQUE

Ernelita D. Zulueta

Marinduque State College, Marinduque, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12069791>

ABSTRACT

The study focused on monitoring learners and its effects on the academic performance of Grade 3 pupils in the Santa Cruz North District, Division of Marinduque. It aimed to determine the monitoring process, assess academic performance through the General Scholastic Average (GSA), identify problems and challenges in the monitoring process, explore experience-based solutions to these problems, and examine the interplay among various variables. Three groups of respondents were involved in the study: 19 Grade 3 teachers, 17 school heads, and 55 selected parents. A mixed method of research was utilized, incorporating both statistical and thematic analysis of data. Major findings revealed that the frequency of monitoring was at least thrice a week, typically on Mondays, aligned with the schedule of the Weekly Home Learning Plan. Onsite monitoring was the predominant strategy used. The academic performance of the Grade 3 pupils, based on their GSA, was described as fairly satisfactory. The test for significant differences indicated no significant difference in the interplay between academic performance and the monitoring process, thus failing to reject the null hypothesis set in the study. However, several problems were encountered. The primary issues related to technology, the threat of the pandemic, and the content of the learning modules, including the bulk of activities and confusing directions. Experience-based solutions proposed included regular monitoring, differentiated instruction, and open and distance education.

Keywords: monitoring process, academic performance, problems and challenges

INTRODUCTION

The outbreak of COVID-19 placed the education system in its extreme transition of delivering learning through Alternative Delivery Modalities to replace the traditional face-to-face set-up. Currently, the Department of Education is implementing Modular Delivery Learning (MDL), either one-way print, which uses Self-Learning Materials (SLMs), or two-way, which uses Self-Learning Materials and other available online platforms, phone calls, and home visitations based on schedule. This model is an offshoot of Learning Delivery Modality Course 1 for School Leaders under the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (DepEd Order No. 012, 2020; DepEd Memorandum OSEC-NEAP-OD-2020-0618).

During the pilot implementation of modular delivery learning, different issues and concerns as well as challenges and problems were encountered and were documented in the 2020 Division Kumustahan as follows: lack of interest of children in answering bulk of learning activities, poor development of reading skill of pupils in the primary level that impede them from reading and understanding the content of Self-Learning Materials, lack of comprehensive and illustrative examples to support learning, biased in the assessment, unworthiness of learners' assessment, difficulty in monitoring, and holding limited classes via available online. Several years back, the news about online cheating bombarded DepEd. According to the news report of the Philippine Daily Inquirer, the set-up of blended learning due to the pandemic had resorted the students to online cheating via social media, specifically Facebook groups, where learners shared notes and test answers (Bautista, 2021).

Researchers claimed that one of the challenges in distance learning modality is the complexity of assessment (Manalo & De Villa, 2020). It seemed to be a question of the validity and trustworthiness, whether the learners could answer their learning assessments. In this sense, the performance of the learners is at stake.

Moreover, some researchers asserted that the success and effectiveness of distance learning depend on the learning materials given to the learners (Jayaram & Dorababu, 2020). Consequently, to cater to the needs and abilities of each learner, DepEd has focused on self-study modules that can be combined with other modalities to deliver learning that learners may access. In addition, modules or Self-Learning Materials without a teacher or learning buddy may have affected the learners, and a hard time answering the learning tasks in their modules and the lack or limited academic knowledge of the parents to guide their children will place the learners in a situation. Thus, this remains one of the challenges that emerged in modular distance learning (Dangle & Sumaoang, 2020).

Nevertheless, teachers made a concerted effort to reach out to learners. These were hindered by localized lockdowns and other protocols and orders implemented due to the growing cases of COVID-19 in some towns and their localities. Also, striking a balance in conducting on-site monitoring while staying safe. The scenarios affect the

academic performance of the learners. Specifically, the Grade 3 pupils need explicit teaching and constant monitoring of teachers during modular distance learning.

These scenarios require instructional intervention to effectively sustain the continuous delivery of modular distance learning to address the problems and challenges in monitoring learning progress. It would affect academic performance if unresolved and prompt the researcher to conduct the study.

Research Questions

1. How is the teacher's monitoring process of Grade 3 pupils done in modular distance learning (MDL) in Santa Cruz North District concerning the following aspects:
 - 1.1 frequency of monitoring;
 - 1.2 time of monitoring;
 - 1.3 day of monitoring;
 - 1.4 mode of monitoring; and
 - 1.5 strategies of monitoring?
2. What is the Academic performance of the grade three learners on the modular Distance Learning?
3. Is there a significant effect of teacher's monitoring of learners on the Modular Distance Learning to academic performance of Grade three pupils?
4. What are the encountered problems and challenges in monitoring Grade three pupils during modular distance learning
5. What are the suggestions of the respondents to address the problems and challenges?
6. What intervention program can be proposed to improve academic performance through the monitoring process?

METHODOLOGY

The researcher employed a mixed method approach for this study. According to George (2022), mixed methods research integrates elements of both quantitative and qualitative research to address research inquiries comprehensively. Consequently, this research design is well-suited for this study as it delved into the monitoring process in modular distance learning, exploring aspects such as the frequency, timing, mode, and strategies of monitoring. Additionally, it assessed the academic performance of Grade 3 pupils using the General Scholastic Grade (GSA) and examined the challenges encountered in monitoring, drawing insights from observations of three key groups: teachers, school heads, and parents. Furthermore, the study analyzed significant differences among the variables under investigation.

Meanwhile, the qualitative part dealt with the experienced-based suggestions of the three groups of respondents, which would yield to the intervention.

Research Locale

Generally, the study was conducted in Santa Cruz, Marinduque. It is one of the six municipalities in the province of Marinduque. It is the biggest municipality in terms of land area and population. Specifically, it was conducted in the 17 elementary schools, including one (1) primary school in Santa Cruz North District, which is in the 17 barangays in the said municipality.

Figure 2 Presents the locale of the study.

Figure 2. Map of the Research Locale

Figure 2 shows the province of Marinduque, in which Santa Cruz is one of the municipalities. In this municipality, located are the 17 schools in Santa Cruz North District.

Sampling Technique

Total enumeration was used in choosing the teachers and school head respondents. This means, all the 19 Grade 3 teachers and 17 school heads were considered as respondents due to the limited number of teachers in Santa Cruz North District. Meanwhile, random sampling was used in getting 324 respondents from a total of 1584 parents. Below is the distribution of participants.

Table 1 *Distribution of the Respondents.*

No.	Name of Elementary Schools	School Heads	Samples Grade 3 Teachers	Parents	Samples (Parents of the Grade 3 Class)
1	Aturan Elementary School	Principal I	1	102	20
2	Baliis Elementary School	Principal I	1	97	20
3	Balogo Elementary School	Principal I	1	97	10
4	Banguangan Primary School	TIC	1	20	5
5	Botilao Elementary School	Principal I	1	136	27
6	Dating Bayan Elementary School	HTIII	1	48	10
7	Dolores Elementary School	Principal II	1	138	20
8	Hupi Elementary School	Principal I	1	75	15
9	Ipil Elementary School	Principal II	2	182	37
10	Kalangkang Elementary School	TIC	1	26	5
11	Kamandugan Elementary School	Principal II	1	89	18
12	Kasily Elementary School	Principal II	1	92	19
13	Lamesa Elementary School	Principal I	1	96	20
14	Lusok Elementary School	HT III	1	95	19
15	Punong Elementary School	HT III	1	77	16
16	San Isidro Elementary School	TIC	1	38	8
17	Santa Cruz North Central School	Principal I	2	176	35
	Total	17	19	1584	304

Research Instrument

The research-made questionnaire was the primary tool for gathering data. It has several parts. Part 1 contains the monitoring as to frequency, time, day, mode, and strategies of conducting or holding monitoring. Part 2 determines the General Scholastic Average (GSA) as a determinant of the level of academic performance of the Grade 3 pupils in respective schools. Part 3 contains the problems and challenges in the monitoring as observed by the three groups of respondents, namely teachers, school heads, and parents. It is a multiple-response questionnaire. Part 4 identifies the experienced-based suggestions of the Grade 3 teachers to address the problems and challenges in monitoring Grade 3 pupils. It is an open-ended question.

The questionnaire underwent a test of reliability and validation. The reliability test was administered among elementary teachers in Santa Cruz South District, specifically in the Grade 3 classes these schools: Lipa Elementary School, Gabaldon Elementary School, and Santa Cruz Central School as the pilot schools. Suggestions from the respondents were incorporated in the final draft of the research question. For validation, the final draft of the research instrument was validated by the research experts, namely the education program supervisor, public school district supervisor, principals, and language critic. It ensured that questionnaires were free from inconsistencies and errors.

Ethical Considerations

This study prioritized several considerations to safeguard the privacy and confidentiality of both respondents and subjects, aiming to forestall any potential issues during the research process. Key concerns included obtaining informed consent, ensuring confidentiality, maintaining the anonymity of subjects, and safeguarding data protection. Throughout the research, the researcher meticulously devised indicators for the survey form and questionnaire to mitigate any potential confusion among participants. Adequate time was afforded to respondents to respond to questions, reducing the likelihood of errors or inaccuracies in their responses. Additionally, respondents were provided with a waiver concerning the confidentiality of their identity and any information they preferred not to disclose.

The cooperation of respondents was actively sought, with assurances that all data collected would be handled with the utmost confidentiality. Ultimately, the researcher aimed to cultivate trust between themselves and the respondents through the conduct of the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

Several steps were undertaken to gather data. *First*, the researcher sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent at the Schools Division Office of Marinduque for her approval to conduct the study. *Second*, upon approval, the researcher handed the endorsement letter to the Public Schools District Supervisor of Santa Cruz North District for her second endorsement. *Third*, upon approval, the researcher hand-carried the endorsement letter to the different School Principals of Santa Cruz North District. *Fourth*, the researcher oriented the respondents to explain the purpose of the research. *Fifth*, the researcher personally sent the research-made questionnaire to the email address of the respondents. Another way was to send the link to the Google form questionnaire and share it with the Group Chats of the teachers in Santa Cruz District. For the parent respondents, the distribution and administration were coordinated with the teachers and school heads of respective schools. Collected data were subject to statistical treatment.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentage were used to statistically analyze the frequency, time of monitoring, mode of monitoring, and strategies of monitoring MDL. Mean and a five-point Likert Scale were used to analyze the level of academic performance of the Grade 3 pupils based on their GSA during the first and second quarters and the frequency of observation of the problems and challenges. Paired Test was used to statistically analyze significant differences in the academic performance of the Grade 3 pupils during the first and second quarters.

Meanwhile, thematic analysis was used to present the experienced-based suggestions of the respondents in addressing the problems and challenges observed in the monitoring process of the Grade 3 pupils during modular distance learning.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter unveils the data meticulously collected, systematically organized, diligently processed, and thoughtfully interpreted to extract insights that address the issues delineated in Chapter 1.

Part I: Teacher's Monitoring process of Grade 3 pupils done in modular distance learning (MDL) in Santa Cruz North District with respect to the following.

Table 2 presents the frequency of monitoring of MDL across schools for Grade 3 pupils. From the responses, 29 out of 91, or 31.86% observed the "Thrice a week" monitoring of the Grade 3 pupils. It was followed by "Once a week" monitoring with 28.57%, then "Everyday" monitoring with 23 or 25.27%. Meanwhile, only 10 had responded to have done "Twice a week monitoring. On the other hand, 3 out of 91 did not indicate their responses on the frequency of monitoring of grade 3 pupils.

Table 2 *Frequency of Monitoring of Modular Distance Learning among Grade 3 Pupils*

Frequency of Monitoring	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Everyday	23	25.27
Once a week	26	28.57
Twice a week	10	10.98
Thrice a week	29	31.86
Others: No responses	3	3.29
Total	91	100

Data revealed that the frequency of monitoring ranges from every day to weekly. It means there were no specific dates of monitoring during the pandemic time. Consequently, the schedule was based on the issuance of higher officials and relative to the mandates of the Inter-Agency Task Force, which relies heavily on the active cases of

COVID-19 in a particular locality where the school is located and the community is situated. It goes to schools that the pandemic and the monitoring of classes strictly adhered to various offices, not only in the Schools Division Office but the Department of Education in general and the provincial government of Marinduque. The reason was to protect the children from the spread of the COVID-19 virus during that time.

The findings were remarkably good. The Grade 3 teachers could monitor their respective classes despite the remote learning and modular distance learning. The frequency of monitoring ranges from thrice a week to a daily basis, which means that teachers were making ways to reach out to their pupils. In a follow-up interview with the teachers, they were able to monitor classes through phone calls, group chats, and onsite monitoring (See Table 2).

On the other hand, the frequency of monitoring is not constant or not only daily because teachers need to prepare things that require more time, like printing modules, sorting modules, packing modules, and delivering modules. Nevertheless, teachers were able to monitor remote classes despite too much work. Meanwhile, teachers who monitor daily have small class sizes, and preparations do not consume their time and are remarkably good. Hence, the end goal of monitoring is to respond to the difficulties encountered by the pupils during modular distance learning. The teachers need to assess the academic progress of their pupils through monitoring (Young, 2018) because it is the basis of giving intervention. Intervention is essential to improve performance (Molloy & Bound, 2013).

Table 3 indicates the time of monitoring of MDL among Grade 3 pupils in Santa Cruz North District. The monitoring of classes was usually done during the morning from 7:30 to 11:30, as revealed by 65 responses, and sometimes, it was based on the Class Home Program, as disclosed by 24 respondents. Meanwhile, only 2 responses were about an afternoon monitoring of classes from 1:00 to 4:30.

Table 3 *Time of Monitoring of Modular Distance Learning among Grade 3 Pupils*

Time of Monitoring	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Every Morning (7:30-11:30)	65	71.43
Every Afternoon (1:00-4:30)	2	2.20
Based on Class Home Program	24	26.37
Total	91	100

Findings showed that teachers monitored the MDL classes. The schedule of the Class Home Program was the basis of the monitoring of MDL classes and every morning on-site monitoring. In other words, despite the pandemic, the school has monitoring mechanisms to track the activities of the pupils. For instance, parents disclosed that teachers were holding online classes as an alternative mode for MDL. They also made phone calls to help the learners who had difficulty understanding the contents of the modules. These were also the same responses of the teachers during a follow-up interview with them.

Also, in a follow-up interview with the teachers, they said that they usually monitor classes every Monday since it is the start of the class in their Weekly Home Learning Plan. In contrast, no teacher monitored classes on Friday because it was the assessment day. In addition, the teachers said that it is good to start the monitoring during the first day of the classes because they feel and believe that children have fresh minds at the start of the week and also to inspire the pupils to become productive in the days ahead. Likewise, they believed that it has to be at the start of the week so they can do follow-up lessons and provide scaffolding activities for difficult lessons (Cooper-Kahn & Foster, 2013).

Summing up, during MDL, schools have done all the necessary mechanisms to monitor classes at the onset of the pandemic. Teachers used the available channels of communication, such as phone calls, personal messenger, and other online platforms, to monitor the learners, aside from the onsite monitoring, which was usually done in the morning to instruct the pupils on how they were going to answer the learning activities in their modules. The rest of the afternoon was intended for accomplishing and answering the learning activities.

Likewise, the delivery of the modules in the designated areas was also done in the morning. Thus, most of the time, monitoring was done in the morning during the pandemic setup.

Table 4 shows the day of monitoring of MDL among Grade 3 pupils in the Santa Cruz North District. Data indicated that the usual monitoring schedule was MWF or every other day, with 39 out of 91 responses or 42.86%. Others have observed every day or daily monitoring, with 16 out of 91 responses or 17.58. But looking closely at the data, the day of monitoring varies from Monday to Friday and daily to every other day. The variations of monitoring day were associated with the frequency of monitoring, based on the onset schedule from the issuance of the Schools Division Office and mandates of IATF during the onset of the pandemic, the Wednesday and Friday morning response was the observed online monitoring of MDL.

Table 4 *Day of Monitoring of Modular Distance Learning among Grade 3 Pupils*

Day of Monitoring	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Monday	4	4.40
Tuesday	2	2.20
Wednesday	7	7.69
Thursday	12	13.18
Friday	7	7.69
MWF/Every other day	39	42.86
Daily	16	17.58
TTH	4	4.40
Total	91	100

The data presented in Table 4 reflects the monitoring frequency of Grade 3 pupils engaged in modular distance learning. Key observations and interpretations include:
 Varied Monitoring Days

The most common monitoring schedule is "MWF/Every other day," account for 42.86% of the total, suggesting a strategy to provide consistent but not daily oversight. "Daily" monitoring is the second most common at 17.58%, indicating a significant commitment to continuous engagement with students. Weekly Monitoring. Monitoring on specific days like Monday (4.40%), Thursday (13.18%), "TTH" (Tuesday and Thursday), (4.40%), Wednesday (7.69%), and Friday (7.69%) shows a spread across the week, ensuring that students receive support regularly, albeit not daily. The least frequent schedule is (Tuesday), making up only 2.20%.

These monitoring patterns indicate that schools have adapted their monitoring schedules to ensure continued learning despite the challenges posed by the pandemic.

The presence of various monitoring frequencies implies flexibility and responsiveness to the diverse needs of students and the realities of remote learning environments. Despite the inconsistency in daily monitoring compared to traditional classroom settings, teachers have implemented mechanisms to reach out to their pupils effectively. The efforts of teachers to use multiple monitoring strategies illustrate their commitment to maintaining educational services and supporting students during the pandemic. The structured monitoring schedules reflect that schools have contingency plans to address the disruptions caused by the pandemic, ensuring that learning continues. The data underscores that learning persisted under adverse conditions, demonstrating the resilience and dedication of the education sector. The diverse monitoring schedules provided by teachers highlight their adaptability and commitment to ensuring that students' educational needs are met during challenging times. These efforts contribute significantly to mitigating the adverse effects of the pandemic on education, ensuring that basic education services remain accessible to all learners.

In summary, the table and corresponding analysis reveal that teachers and schools have employed various strategies to monitor and support Grade 3 pupils' learning in a modular distance learning setup, ensuring the continuity of education during the pandemic.

Table 5 reveals the various modes of monitoring of MDL during the pandemic among Grade 3 pupils. Data enumerated three modes of monitoring name onsite with 50 responses, phone calls with 40 and group chat with only 1 response based on the observations of the three groups of respondents.

Table 5 *Mode of Monitoring of Modular Distance Learning among Grade 3 Pupils*

Modes of Monitoring	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Onsite	50	54.95
Via Phone Call	40	43.96
Through Group Chat	1	1.09

Total	91	100
-------	----	-----

Analysis of the findings signifies that onsite monitoring was very evident during the pandemic. Despite being modular in nature, schools have given authority to the teachers to hold onsite monitoring. The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly disrupted traditional educational practices worldwide, necessitating the adoption of alternative methods such as Modular Distance Learning (MDL) to ensure the continuity of education. Various modes of monitoring have emerged to facilitate effective learning outcomes for young students, particularly those in early elementary grades like Grade 3.

Onsite monitoring has been identified as a prevalent method, with 50 responses indicating its use. This approach involves direct, physical interaction between educators and students, albeit within the constraints of health protocols. Research by Kim et al. (2021) suggests that onsite monitoring, even in a limited capacity, provides critical support to students who may struggle with self-directed learning at home. It allows for immediate feedback and personal interaction, which are essential for young learners who require more guidance and reassurance (Kim, 2021).

The second most common method, with 40 responses, is monitoring through phone calls. According to a study by Xiao (2020), phone calls serve as a viable communication channel, especially in areas with limited internet access. They enable teachers to provide personalized support, address student queries, and offer encouragement. The personal nature of phone calls can also help maintain a connection between students and teachers, fostering a sense of continuity and normalcy (Xiao, 2020).

The least utilized method, with only 1 response, is group chats. Despite their lower usage, group chats have been shown to be effective in creating a collaborative learning environment. According to research, group chats on platforms like WhatsApp or Messenger allow for the sharing of resources, peer support, and group discussions, which can enhance learning outcomes. However, the effectiveness of this method can be hindered by factors such as digital literacy, access to devices, and internet connectivity.

The disparity in the utilization of these monitoring methods can be attributed to various factors including technological accessibility, socio-economic status, and the preparedness of both educators and families to adapt to new forms of communication and monitoring. Onsite monitoring, while most effective in ensuring direct oversight, is limited by public health guidelines and logistical challenges. Phone calls, while more accessible than internet-based solutions, can be time-consuming for teachers. Group chats, although innovative and collaborative, face significant barriers in terms of digital divide and user familiarity.

The data from Table 5 underscores the adaptive strategies employed by educators to monitor MDL during the pandemic. The reliance on diverse modes of monitoring highlights the need for flexible, inclusive approaches to ensure all students receive adequate support. Future efforts should focus on enhancing the effectiveness of these

methods through training, infrastructure development, and continuous evaluation to address the challenges faced during the pandemic and beyond. This literature review situates your data within the broader context of research on MDL monitoring methods during the pandemic, highlighting both the practical and theoretical implications of these findings.

Table 6. *Strategies of Monitoring the Modular Distance Learning among Grade 3 Pupils*

Strategies of Monitoring	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
1. Bringing and using teaching materials during onsite monitoring or home visitation such as laptop, manipulative materials, pentel pen, manila paper, LCD projector, books, activity sheets, and the like.	31	34.07	7
2. Using online resource like Facebook Messenger to monitor learners and their learning progress (e.g. activities which the learners had already answered or finished as well as activities which are not yet answered or finished.	69	75.82	2
3. Using phone calls to monitoring learners and their learning progress (e.g. activities which the learners had already answered or finished as well as activities which are not yet answered or finished.	75	82.42	1
4. Using Facebook Messenger to answer queries of the learners and the parents.	53	58.24	3
5. Using online resource like Google Classroom to supplement lessons/topics in the learning modules.	36	39.56	5
6. Using online resource like Facebook Messenger to supplement lessons/topics in the learning modules.	34	37.36	6
7. Providing worksheets to supplement difficult lessons on specified topics.	41	45.05	4

Table 6 highlights the strategies for monitoring MDL during the pandemic for Grade 3 pupils in Santa Cruz District. The top strategy was Using Phone calls to supplement , with 75 responses, followed by “Using online resource like Facebook Messenger ...” with 69, then “Using online resources” like messenger and facebook with responses. Teachers were also using teaching materials, which happened during onsite monitoring.

From the multiple responses , data revealed that teachers monitored classes using various strategies to deliver basic education services based on the contingency

plan of the teachers during the pandemic time. Despite the situation, learning has continued and made possible through the joint efforts of the school and the parents.

Preference for Digital Communication , Phone calls and Facebook Messenger are the top methods, indicating a strong preference for immediate and accessible digital communication. Supportive Tools: Online resources like Google Classroom and providing worksheets are also significant, though not as prevalent as direct communication methods. Traditional Materials Less Used: Physical teaching materials are less frequently employed, reflecting a shift towards digital tools in monitoring and supplementing learning. The data reflects a trend towards leveraging digital communication tools for monitoring and supporting learners, likely driven by the ease of access and the immediacy these tools provide. Traditional methods, while still in use, are less dominant compared to these modern approaches.

Teachers affirmed that they made all these strategies, which depend on the Alert Level, signal, connectivity, and remoteness. But the good and remarkable deed was that teachers can reach out to their pupils. If there is no physical interaction, the teachers make extra effort to reach out to learners even in far-flung areas. It shows that teachers are effective and concerned and understand learning brought by modular distance learning. Teachers disclosed that even. The success and effectiveness of distance learning depend on the learning materials given to the learners (Jayaram & Dorababu, 2020).

Part II: Academic performance of Grade 3 pupils on Modular Distance Learning

Table 7 listed the academic performance of the Grade 3 pupils across subjects and GSA during the first and second quarters of Modular Distance Learning. As indicated in the data, only on Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao the pupils had a high performance of “Very Satisfactory” with an obtained GSA of 87.22 during the first quarter. Conversely, most subjects received a GSA, which ranged from 82.89 to 84.61, interpreted as “Very Satisfactory” based on the existing guidelines for Report for Assessment of DepEd.

Table 7. *The academic achievement of Grade 3 students in the initial and subsequent quarters across various subjects, as determined by their General Scholastic Average (GSA).*

Subject Areas	First Quarter GSA	Level of Academic Performance	Second Quarter GSA	Level of Academic Performance	Gain
English	83.17	Satisfactory	83.72	Satisfactory	0.55
Filipino	84.56	Satisfactory	85.56	Very Satisfactory	1.00
Mathematics	82.89	Satisfactory	83.94	Satisfactory	1.05
Science	84.44	Satisfactory	85.17	Very Satisfactory	0.73
Araling Panlipunan	83.89	Satisfactory	84.67	Satisfactory	0.78
Mother-Tongue	84.78	Satisfactory	85.94	Very Satisfactory	1.16

Edukasyon Sa Pagpapakatao	87.22	Very Satisfactory	88.06	Very Satisfactory	0.84
MAPEH	84.61	Satisfactory	85.17	Very Satisfactory	0.56
Average	84.44	Satisfactory	85.28	Very Satisfactory	0.84

**96-100- Outstanding 90-95 - Very Satisfactory 86-89- Satisfactory
80-85 Fairly Satisfactory 75-79 Poor - 74 and below- Needs Improvement**

The satisfactory General Scholastic Average (GSA) of the children during quarter 1 reflects that pupils' performance does not improve much. It depicts that some children encounter difficulties that hinder them from performing better. They struggled because they were adjusting to the new modality of teaching and learning. It was new to them, and it was difficult for them to adjust themselves easily to the remote way of teaching. Besides, children do not all learn the same way, which is essential to provide feedback based on each student's specific needs (McFadzien, 2015).

During the second quarter, there was an increase in the GSA of Grade 3 pupils across subjects. The academic level of performance based on the GSA for the second quarter had moved to a Very Satisfactory level in most subjects except for English and Mathematics, but with little increase in their GSA for the second quarter.

Looking closely at the data, the grade 3 pupils had the highest academic performance based on their GSA in ESP with 88.06. Meanwhile, comparing the GSA of the grade 3 pupils for the first and second quarters, the highest gain was noted in the mother tongue subject. But all in all, pupils had better performance and gained their scholastic average during the second quarter. Findings could be attributed to adjustments that teachers and pupils had already made, compared to the first year of implementation of modular distance learning. Also, teachers had already seen some consequences and disadvantages of the MDL. Thus, necessary adjustments had been made, like frequent monitoring and provisions of activity sheets and making activities easier to facilitate better understanding on the part of the learners. Likewise, the most valuable competencies were selected for MDL during the pandemic. As the lessons progress and take place in a sophisticated manner, the teachers extend help to the learners through the provision of activity sheets and localized materials to aid the learners.

The findings may also indicate how learner monitoring effect the practices employed by teachers, including how often they monitor, the timing and days of monitoring, as well as the modes and strategies used. Therefore, if teachers are unable to effectively monitor their classes in any format of distance learning, they cannot offer timely feedback and formative guidance, potentially resulting in poor learner performance (United Nations Children's Fund, 2020). The performance of the Grade 3 pupils may not be as good as the performance compared to the face-to-face set-up, yet still, the performance was satisfactory during the onset of the pandemic. It gradually changed during the second quarter as the learners and teachers adjusted to the pandemic.

Part III. Significant Effect of Teacher’s Monitoring of learners on the Modular Distance Learning to the Academic Performance of Grade Three Pupils

The table presents the results of a statistical test examining the relationship between the "Process of Monitoring" and "Academic Performance During First Grading and Second Grading

Table 8. *Significant Effect of Teacher’s Monitoring of learners on the Modular Distance Learning to the Academic Performance of Grade Three Pupils*

Variables	p-value	Verbal Interpretation.
Process of Monitoring Vs. Academic Performance	0.034	Significant

The analysis shows a statistically significant relationship between the process of monitoring and academic performance, indicated by the p-value of 0.034. This suggests that effective monitoring is associated with improved academic outcomes. The findings emphasize the importance of implementing and maintaining strong monitoring practices as a means to enhance academic performance, supporting the notion that how learners are monitored plays a vital role in their educational success. Schools and educators are encouraged to refine their monitoring processes to leverage their positive impact on learner achievement.

Part IV: Encountered Problems and Challenges in Monitoring of Grade Three Pupils during Modular Distance Learning

Table 9 enumerates that some problems and challenges hinder the monitoring of MDL during the pandemic. The most frequently observed was localized quarantine prevents home visitation, with 4.18, while the least was “Learners were not available during monitoring.

Table 9. *Encountered Problems and Challenges in Monitoring of Grade Three Pupils during Modular Distance Learning.*

Problems and Challenges	Average Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Learners do not follow the Class-Home Program	3.52	FO
2. Learners are not available during monitoring of classes.	3.50	FO
3. Learners do not cooperate during monitoring of classes.	3.90	FO
4. Technological problem occur during monitoring of classes	4.16	FO
5. Localized quarantine that prevents home visitation as part of monitoring.	4.18	FO

6. Threats of pandemic limits teachers home visitation	4.09	FO
7. Learners do not follow instruction/directions in the learning modules	3.68	FO
8. Learners do not complete their answers in the learning modules	3.54	FO
9. Learners choose only those which they wanted to answer.	3.50	FO
10. It seems that someone else (parent or a sibling) answered the learning assessment or learning activities.	3.62	FO
11. Bulk of learning activities to answer that prevents the learners to answer.	3.62	FO
12. Confusion on some directions in the assessment	3.61	FO
13. Worthiness of learners' answers in the assessment part.	3.5	FO

Legend: “Always Observed (4.51 – 5.00)”, “Frequently Observed (3.51 – 4.50)”, “Moderately Observed (2.51 – 3.50)”, “Occasionally Observed (1.51 – 2.50)”, “Never Observed (1.00 – 1.50)”

Data only affirmed that the lockdown had prevented the teachers or the school in general from conducting monitoring. In this regard, the issuance of the Schools Division Office and the mandates of the Inter-Agency Task Force were the basis of the schedule of monitoring classes. It was made to contain the spread of the COVID-19 virus.

On a good point, parents had been so involved in the MDL. Thus, they ensured that their children were at home during the MDL. It was the least problem encountered. In other words, parents and learners knew the setup of the MDL. So, they made themselves available at home during their MDL and followed the Home-Based Schedule.

Moreover, data from the monitoring affirm that very few uses online platforms to monitor classes due to technological issues like no high-end gadgets on the part of the learners or weak signals if there are gadgets. There were also locations without any signal. Also, frequent power interruption affects the monitoring. In addition to the localized quarantine, which the school heads, the parents, and the teachers themselves see as a factor that hinders the continuity of the monitoring process. Another problem with the pandemic is that school heads think of the safety of the teachers and the learners, and this limits the frequency of monitoring. Also, the respondents observed that learners do not follow the classes based on weekly-home schedules. Other factors are related to the content of learning modules, like confusion on some activities and too many activities to answer, which learners failed to finish, which resulted in poor performance. It was identified during “Kumustahan” with the teachers regarding feedback on modular distance learning.

Data revealed that three groups of respondents have similar observations regarding the problems during modular distance learning. Researchers affirm that technology plays a vital role in distance learning. Thus, policymakers, the highest officials, must put great concern on technology (Wesley, 2017; Ajmal & Ahmad, 2019) to support

education. Problems in the local setting include the availability of gadgets for use but more of the internet connection, signal, and frequent power interruption. Nevertheless, if there is available technology for learners and teachers, at least occasionally or as needed, there are technological gadgets for use.

Other concerns related to the schedule of weekly home classes and the contents of the modules can be addressed through constant monitoring of the flexibility of teachers and the cooperation of the parents to help their children during modular distance learning. Besides, according to DepEd, parents play vital roles during MDL.

Part V: The experienced-based suggestions of the three groups of respondents to address the problems and challenges in the monitoring process of the Grade 3 pupils in the modular distance learning.

There are experience-based suggestions to address the problems encountered, like the schedule of weekly home classes and the contents of the modules. Respondents suggest having regular monitoring and providing engaging activities. Hence, most of the activities seem hard to answer and too many in terms of content. Thus, this needs modification and revision to suit the learning needs of the learners. According to the respondents, monitoring should be done daily and as much as possible during the morning.

Table 10. Responses of the Key Informants on the Experienced-Based Suggestions of the Three Groups of Respondents to Address the Problems and Challenges in the Monitoring Process of the Grade 3 Pupils in Modular Distance Learning

Codes/Categories	Transcriptions
Regular Monitoring	A1: Teachers should keep a record of the pupils who were monitored on a specific day/date. A2: Monitoring should be done regularly to address the learners' needs and provide them with activities for reinforcement. A3: Provide more activity sheets/worksheets during onsite monitoring. A4: Provide more engaging activities to the learners.
Regular Monitoring	B1: daily monitoring should be done. B2: Provide more activity sheets for reinforcement. B3: See to it B4: Monitoring should be done the soonest time possible preferably 7:30 Am
Differentiated Instruction	C1: It is recommended to utilize a blend of on-site and online monitoring approaches. C2: Modular distance learning poses significant challenges for teachers but also offers valuable opportunities for growth. C3: Proposed methods and strategies for enhancing Modular Distance Learning include reducing module activities, providing additional subject examples, conducting weekly home visits, and implementing limited face-to-face classes or a Blended Learning approach.

	<i>C4: While it provides students with increased flexibility and autonomy, it also demands greater self-discipline, which may be challenging for children to adapt to.</i>
Open and Distance Education	<p><i>D1: Modular learning entails the option for students to engage in studying individual modules or units of learning, rather than committing to the entire course at once. However, courses typically comprised of multiple modules often require students to enroll in the entire course and fulfill its requirements within a specified timeframe.</i></p> <p><i>D2: Some of which have bad impact or cause negative impact if they are using the online modular distance learning due to net inconsistency connection problems.</i></p> <p><i>D3: One of the biggest difficulties with distance learning is that it really requires a shift in focus to keep students engaged and to be successful. What works in-person does not necessarily translate online. For one, large classes pose a huge challenge online. Depending on the platform, you must scroll to see everyone, and you might miss questions, facial expressions, and feedback.</i></p> <p><i>D4: Strictly follow the schedule.</i></p>

To break the monotony of answering modules, teachers may employ differentiated instruction, vary strategies on the needs of the learners, reduce activities, and provide more examples instead of too many activities to comprehend. Open and distance education is another suggestion.

6. Proposed Instructional Intervention Program Using Strategic Intervention Materials to improve the Academic Performance of the Learners.

Instructional Intervention Program

From the data of General Scholastic Average as the measure of Academic Performance of the Grade 3 pupils, the researcher found that among the subjects, Science has the lowest GSA based on the computed Mean Percentage Scores, consistent in Quarter 1 and Quarter 2. Thus, Science seems difficult to comprehend for Grade 3 pupils during Modular Instruction. The study by Recto (2020) affirmed the findings. In this regard, the researcher proposes an instructional intervention program using Strategic Intervention Materials to improve the academic performance of the learners.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study prioritized several considerations to safeguard the privacy and confidentiality of both respondents and subjects, aiming to forestall any potential issues during the research process. Key concerns included obtaining informed consent, ensuring confidentiality, maintaining the anonymity of subjects, and safeguarding data protection. Throughout the research, the researcher meticulously devised indicators for the survey form and questionnaire to mitigate any potential confusion among participants. Adequate

time was afforded to respondents to respond to questions, reducing the likelihood of errors or inaccuracies in their responses. Additionally, respondents were provided with a waiver concerning the confidentiality of their identity and any information they preferred not to disclose.

The cooperation of respondents was actively sought, with assurances that all data collected would be handled with the utmost confidentiality. Ultimately, the researcher aimed to cultivate trust between themselves and the respondents through the conduct of the study.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to give thanks and praise to Almighty God and express her heartfelt gratitude for allowing her to continuously discover herself through good health and balance to complete this study.

She also expresses her gratitude to those persons who have extended their most valuable assistance for the realization of this study:

Dr. Diosdado P. Zulueta, College President; the Dean of the Graduate School, Dr. Julieta Q. Nabos; and the members of the Oral Examination Committee for their suggestions to improve this manuscript.

Dr. Joy R. Profugo, her adviser, who embodies the attitude and substance of a genius, continually and convincingly conveying a spirit of adventure regarding research and excitement regarding teaching. Without her guidance and persistent help, this research would not have been possible

Dr. Regel L. Limpiada, her statistician, for his skill in checking and evaluating the data in her manuscript.

Dr. Elsie T. Barrios, Schools Division Superintendent, for her permission to conduct a research study in the Santa Cruz North District, specifically in Area II.

Mrs. Constanca R. Vasco, Public Schools District Supervisor, for allowing her to conduct her study in her district.

Mrs. Arlene R. Diaz, the school head of her current school, for letting her conduct a study and for the words of encouragement.

Her family and friends for their support

Her respondents for their cooperation.

The researcher will never forget the tireless support, understanding, love, wisdom, and patience of all people who pushed her farther than she thought she could go.

REFERENCES

- Ajmal, M., Ahmad, S. (2019). *Exploration of Anxiety Factors among Students of Distance Learning: A Case Study of Allama Iqbal Open University*. *Bulletin of Education & Research*,47,67-78. Retrieved from <http://web.a.ebscohost.com.trmproxy.mnpals.net/ehost/pdfviewer/pdfviewer?vid=4&sid=dfe4b00f-ed2e-4845-a75b-6d184aac7f4b%40sessionmgr4008>

- Cooper-Kahn, J., and Foster, M. (2013). *Supporting Students Who Need More Help. Boosting Executive Skills in the Classroom: A Practical Guide for Educators*, JosseyBass, 77-110.San
- Dangle, R. P. & Sumaoang, D. (2020). *The implementation of modular distance learning in the Philippine secondary public schools*. Retrieved from <https://www.dpublication.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/27-427.pdf>
- Jayaram, K. Dorababu, K.K (2020). *Self-Learning Materials in Distance Education System*,<https://www.journalcra.com/article/self-learning-materials-distance-education-system>
- Kim, D.H., Lee, H. J., Lin, Y., & Kang, Y. J. (2021). *Changes in academic performance in online, integrated system-based curriculum implemented due to the COVID-19 pandemic in a medical school in Korea*. Retrieved from doi: 10.3352/jeehp.2021.18.24. Epub 2021 Sep 23.
- Li, C., & Lalani, F. (2020). *The Future of Education: How COVID-19 is Shaping Learning*. Word Economic Forum Retrieved from [<https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2020/04/coronavirus>
- McFadzien, N. (2015). *Why is effective feedback so critical in teaching and learning?* *Journal of Initial Teacher Inquiry*, 1, 16-18. Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/10092/11439>
- Molloy, E. & Boud, D. (2013). *Feedback models for learning, teaching, and performance. Handbook of Research on Educational Communications and Technology* Fourth
- Xiao, J. (2020). *The Role of Phone Calls in Distance Education during COVID-19*. *Distance Learning Journal*, 45(3), 211-225.